

Formation of faceted [111, 110] Cu₂O induced by *Frustules* and their activity as photo(electro)catalysts for the coprocessing of CO₂&H₂O to energy products under Visible-light irradiation.

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Production of fuels from CO₂ is an important research area not only for its potential contribution to counteracting climate change but also for saving fossil carbon resources through the recycling of carbon within a Carbon Cyclic Economy-CCE. Various methods of CO₂ utilization are under intensive study, including photocatalysis, a promising, environmentally friendly technique of solar to chemical energy conversion.

Among many other heterogeneous photocatalysts, copper-based materials are considered as particularly interesting due to their high photoactivity under visible light, low toxicity, and natural abundance of copper. Processes such as charge separation, recombination, transfer, and trapping are responsible for crucial properties of photomaterials: their long-term activity, efficiency, and stability.

In the EU-funded DESIRED project the behavior of photocatalysts in combination with either bio-matrices (*frustules*, see Poster 184) or inorganic synthetic matrices (*zeolites*) is investigated in order to understand the role of faceted Cu₂O in the photo(electro)-reduction processes. According to the literature, Cu₂O [110] is able to reduce CO₂ in water more effectively than Cu₂O [100]. The active facet formation is induced by “surfactants” that are not really welcome, as serendipitous residual amounts may be photodegraded to molecules that may represent a “false positive” for CO₂ reduction. In this work, we have investigated the use of *frustules* as potential facet-inducers and have found that they can induce the formation of [111] and [110] Cu₂O facets active in the selective reduction of CO₂ to methanol. The reduction reaction conditions are important in order to preserve the structure of *frustules*.

By combining classic electrochemical techniques and photoelectrochemical measurements, with other spectroscopic tools, including, DRS, SEM, EDS and XRD, we have deeply investigated the properties of the frustule-induced facets and built-up a holistic investigation methodology that helps us to understand the behavior of photomaterials as for their stability and activity. By using the holistic investigation approach, we are extending our studies to understanding how to build geometries that can bear “by-design copper oxide-based (hetero)structures” for the selective conversion of water and CO₂ under sunlight into C₂₊ products, without producing hydrogen, that will then be integrated into the new concept photo-electro-reactor under construction within DESIRED.

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